

Figure S8. Differentially expressed proteins in the saliva between the OFC-positive and OFC-negative groups before OFC

Colored areas in the volcano plot show the differentially expressed proteins upregulated and downregulated in the OFC-positive group relative to the OFC-negative group. Proteome analysis of saliva samples was performed using four biological replicates for the OFC-positive group and five biological replicates for the OFC-negative group.